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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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Kulayan ng Kulturang Pilipino

From little islands to huge mountains,
Our culture is vibrant and unites us all.
Sayaw, dasal, sa bawat awit,
May diwang banal, may pusong tapat.

Warm smiles, a helping hand,
displays bayanihan all around the country.
Sa hirap, ginhawa, tayo'y kasama,
Lakas ng loob, ating sandata.

The sound of drums, the pounding of feet,
We encounter joy at every fiesta.
Bawat kulintang at tugtog ng t'nalak,
Nagkukuwento ng lahing wagas.

We communicate politely, po and opo,
We always exhibit signs of respect.
Mula sa bata hanggang matanda,
Paggalang ay ugali nating dala.

Our food, our crafts, our ancient tales,
Are treasures more valuable than gold?
Adobo, barong, and banig na habi
Tatlong simbolo ng ating pagkasi.

Let's cherish our language, wikang mahal.
Taglay ang kultura and dangal.
Speaking Filipino unites our hearts.
Our future is bright, and our soul is radiant.

Raise the red, blue, and white flag of our country.
Let it wave in the sunshine of freedom.
Tatak ng dangal, ating bandila
Walang kapantay, pag-ibig sa bayan.

Thus, let us advocate, protect, and declare,
The spark of our country is the Filipino soul.
Sa puso at gawa, buhay culture,
Wag nawang mawalay, kulay ng lahi.